

Repository Crisis Scorecards (RCS)

Welcome to the Repository Crisis Scorecards (RCS)

The Repository Crisis Scorecards (RCS) is a self-assessment tool designed to help repositories reflect on their resilience, identify areas of strength, and prioritize opportunities for improvement.

The RCS is intended to support internal learning, planning, and discussion. It is **not** a formal audit, certification, or external evaluation.

What to Expect

This survey takes approximately **20–30 minutes** to complete.

You will be asked to rate a set of statements about your repository's current practices across areas such as:

- Data Stewardship
- Infrastructure & Staffing
- Software
- Cybersecurity & Access Control
- Crisis Response & Recovery
- Networks, Partnerships & Community
- Sustainability & Continuity

Please answer each question based on how well it reflects your repository's current practices. If a question does not apply to your repository, you may select **N/A**.

Your Report

At the end of the survey, you will receive a **Repository Crisis Scorecards Report** that summarizes your completed assessment, including scores, interpretation, identified strengths and recommended areas for improvement.

Privacy and Data Use

This survey does **not** ask for personally identifiable information. Any demographic or contextual information collected is used to better understand how the RCS is being used across different repository contexts.

ESIP's Data Privacy Policy is available here: <https://www.esipfed.org/about/data-privacy-policy/>

Questions

For questions about the RCS or this survey, please contact: esip-sustainablem@lists.esipfed.org

Thank you for contributing to this community effort to strengthen the resilience of research data repositories.

About Your Repository

The questions on this page help us understand the diversity of repositories utilizing the Repository Crisis Scorecards (RCS).

1) How would you identify yourself?*

- User of data housed in a repository: I deposit and/or access and use data stored in repositories for my work or research.
- Administrator or manager of a data repository: I oversee repository operations, policies, staffing, or strategic direction.
- Scientific and technical staff at a data repository: I contribute to the day-to-day operation, curation, or maintenance of a repository.
- Citizen archivist: I help to identify, collect, and archive data from public repositories.

2) Please select the country where your repository is primarily located or administered.*

() LIST OF COUNTRIES

3) Which subject areas does your repository primarily support?*

- Humanities – Languages, Literature, Philosophy, History, Arts, Religion
- Social Sciences – Sociology, Psychology, Education, Economics, Law, Political Science
- Life Sciences – Biology, Ecology, Microbiology, Agriculture, Forestry, Veterinary Sciences
- Health and Medicine – Public Health, Clinical Medicine, Nursing, Pharmacy, Biomedical Research
- Physical Sciences – Physics, Chemistry, Astronomy, Materials Science
- Mathematics and Statistics – Pure and Applied Mathematics, Statistics
- Earth and Environmental Sciences – Geology, Geography, Oceanography, Atmospheric and Climate Science, Hydrology
- Engineering and Technology – Mechanical, Civil, Electrical, Chemical, Industrial, and Systems Engineering
- Computer and Information Sciences – Computer Science, Data Science, Artificial Intelligence, Information Technology
- Interdisciplinary Research – Cross-domain, multidisciplinary, or emerging fields (e.g., sustainability, data science, digital humanities)
- Arts and Cultural Heritage – Creative arts, performance, cultural preservation, and museum collections

4) How is the repository's data most commonly used?*

- Community or local knowledge use – Indigenous, local, or community-based data use and decision-making
 - Nonprofit, advocacy, or media use – transparency, communication, or public awareness activities
 - Operational or crisis response – monitoring or responding to real-time events (e.g., disaster, health, environment)
 - Policy and decision-making – informing policy, regulation, or program evaluation
 - Private sector or industry use – product design, market forecasting, risk assessment, or innovation
 - Repository or infrastructure operations – system management, metadata curation, or interoperability
 - Research and academic use – analyses, model development, replication, and teaching
 - Other - Write In (Required): _____ *
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Section A: Data Stewardship

Please rate each statement by selecting the option that best reflects your current repository practices.

1 = Not in Place 2 = Limited / ad hoc 3 = Partially in place 4 = Mostly in place 5 = Fully in place

If a question does not apply to your repository, you may select N/A, but please use this option sparingly. Additional guidance and examples for each question are provided in the table below.

Data Stewardship*

	1	2	3	4	5	N/A
A1. To what extent does the repository maintain multiple independent copies of its data stored at geographically separated facilities within the same country?	()	()	()	()	()	()
A2. To what extent does the repository maintain at least one independent copy of its data stored at a facility located in a different country than its primary location?	()	()	()	()	()	()
A3. To what extent does the repository maintain offline or air-gapped copies of its data in a secure, controlled environment?	()	()	()	()	()	()
A4. To what extent does the repository use diverse storage media types to reduce the risk of data loss?	()	()	()	()	()	()
A5. To what extent is the repository's data replicated or mirrored by other organizations such that its loss would not create an irreplaceable gap in the broader data ecosystem?	()	()	()	()	()	()
A6. To what extent is dataset metadata complete, accurate, and sufficient for an independent user to understand and reuse the data?	()	()	()	()	()	()
A7. To what extent does the repository follow FAIR principles in how its datasets are described and made accessible?	()	()	()	()	()	()
A8. To what extent do the repository's datasets have associated data management plans (DMPs) that document related publications, datasets, and intended data use?	()	()	()	()	()	()
A9. To what extent has the repository addressed ethical considerations in how datasets are described, governed, and made accessible?	()	()	()	()	()	()
A10. To what extent does the repository have a formal process for periodically evaluating and deprecating datasets that are outdated, superseded, or no longer appropriate to host?	()	()	()	()	()	()

Supporting Guidance

This section evaluates how well the repository protects, replicates, and documents its data to ensure it survives a crisis and remains usable.

Use the descriptions below for additional guidance when answering the questions in this section.

#	Question	Guidance
A1	National replication	Consider whether copies are held at distinct physical locations on separate power grids. Copies housed in the same building or campus, or using RAID arrays, do not qualify as independent copies.
A2	International replication	Consider copies held at facilities outside the repository's home country. This includes self-managed international facilities and contracted cloud or co-location services located abroad.
A3	Offline or air-gapped copies	Offline copies are disconnected from any network to prevent tampering, ransomware, or bit rot.
A4	Storage media diversity	Examples of diverse media include hard drives, tape, cloud storage, and optical media. Relying on a single media type scores lower.
A5	External replication by others	Consider whether other repositories, networks, or organizations hold complete or partial copies of the repository's data independently. A repository that is the sole known source of its datasets scores lowest.
A6	Metadata completeness	Consider required and optional fields, machine-readability, and alignment with community metadata standards.
A7	FAIR compliance	Consider whether datasets are Findable (e.g., assigned persistent identifiers (PIDs) and have landing pages), Accessible (e.g., retrievable via standard protocols), Interoperable (e.g., use recognized vocabularies and metadata schemas), and Reusable (e.g., clear licensing and provenance information).
A8	Data management plans	Consider whether DMPs are attached to datasets at the point of deposit, whether they are kept up to date, and whether they reference related publications and datasets sufficiently for an independent user to understand the broader context of the data.
A9	Ethical considerations	Examples: CARE principles, Local Contexts notices, indigenous data sovereignty, and fine-grained data governance. Mark N/A if no datasets raise these concerns.
A10	Dataset deprecation process	Consider whether datasets are reviewed on a regular schedule, whether deprecation decisions are documented and communicated to users in advance, and whether deprecated datasets are handled in a way that preserves citations and minimizes disruption to dependent workflows.

Section B: Infrastructure & Staffing

Please rate each statement by selecting the option that best reflects your current repository practices.

1 = Not in Place 2 = Limited / ad hoc 3 = Partially in place 4 = Mostly in place 5 = Fully in place

If a question does not apply to your repository, you may select N/A, but please use this option sparingly. Additional guidance and examples for each question are provided in the table below.

Infrastructure & Staffing*

	1	2	3	4	5	N/A
B1. To what extent is the repository's physical infrastructure resilient against disruptions to power, cooling, or building systems?	()	()	()	()	()	()
B2. To what extent is the repository staffed and cross-trained to maintain operations if a key team member is unavailable?	()	()	()	()	()	()
B3. To what extent does the repository have a documented succession plan for key leadership and decision-making roles?	()	()	()	()	()	()
B4. To what extent do staff have access to required training and ongoing professional development opportunities?	()	()	()	()	()	()
B5. To what extent are data backups performed consistently, automated, and regularly tested for successful restoration?	()	()	()	()	()	()
B6. To what extent has the repository identified and mitigated risks associated with dependence on external vendors or service providers for critical operations?	()	()	()	()	()	()

Supporting Guidance

This section evaluates the resilience of the repository's physical infrastructure and people to ensure operations can continue when systems or staff are unavailable.

Use the descriptions below for additional guidance when answering the questions in this section.

#	Question	Guidance
B1	Physical infrastructure	Consider redundant power supplies, HVAC systems, emergency generators, and routine maintenance protocols.
B2	Staff cross-training and coverage	Consider whether roles are documented, staff can cover for each other, and no single person is a critical dependency.
B3	Leadership succession planning	Consider whether responsibilities and authorities are documented and whether designated successors are identified and prepared for critical roles.
B4	Staff training and development	Consider both mandatory onboarding and optional continuing education such as conferences or certifications.
B5	Backup schedule and testing	Consider backup frequency, whether backups are automated, and whether restores are periodically verified.
B6	Vendor and supply chain risk	Consider whether alternative vendors or contingency arrangements are in place for critical services such as cloud storage, hardware, and software licensing.

Section C: Software

Please rate each statement by selecting the option that best reflects your current repository practices.

1 = Not in Place 2 = Limited / ad hoc 3 = Partially in place 4 = Mostly in place 5 = Fully in place

If a question does not apply to your repository, you may select N/A, but please use this option sparingly. Additional guidance and examples for each question are provided in the table below.

Software*

	1	2	3	4	5	N/A
C1. To what extent can the repository's data be accessed and interpreted using freely available or standard tools, without requiring specialized or proprietary software?	()	()	()	()	()	()
C2. To what extent is the software used to operate the repository open source, actively maintained, and free from restrictive licensing?	()	()	()	()	()	()
C3. To what extent is the repository's software sufficiently documented for a technically skilled user to independently install and configure it?	()	()	()	()	()	()

Supporting Guidance

This section evaluates whether the repository's software environment supports long-term data accessibility, recovery, and maintainability.

Use the descriptions below for additional guidance when answering the questions in this section.

#	Question	Guidance
C1	Data accessibility without proprietary software	Consider whether data is available in open, standard formats such as CSV, plain text, or PDF. Relying on a single proprietary tool to access or interpret the data scores lowest.
C2	Software licensing and maintenance	Consider whether the software is openly licensed, whether it has an active developer community or vendor support, and whether the repository would be at risk if the software were discontinued or a license were revoked.
C3	Technical installation documentation	Consider whether installation guides, configuration documentation, and deployment images or scripts are available and up to date.

Section D: Cybersecurity & Access Control

Please rate each statement by selecting the option that best reflects your current repository practices.

1 = Not in Place 2 = Limited / ad hoc 3 = Partially in place 4 = Mostly in place 5 = Fully in place

If a question does not apply to your repository, you may select N/A, but please use this option sparingly. Additional guidance and examples for each question are provided in the table below.

Cybersecurity & Access Control*

	1	2	3	4	5	N/A
D1. To what extent are system and repository-level activities logged, monitored, and able to trigger alerts for anomalous behavior?	()	()	()	()	()	()
D2. To what extent are staff permissions appropriately scoped, with additional safeguards for sensitive actions such as data deletion or system changes?	()	()	()	()	()	()
D3. To what extent does the repository have access to qualified cybersecurity expertise to support the regular review and security of its systems?	()	()	()	()	()	()

Supporting Guidance

This section evaluates how well the repository protects its systems and data from unauthorized access, accidental loss, and malicious activity.

Use the descriptions below for additional guidance when answering the questions in this section.

#	Question	Guidance
D1	Activity logging and monitoring	Consider whether logging is automated, real-time, and reviewed before changes are pushed to offsite copies.
D2	Access controls	Consider role-based access controls, multi-factor authentication, deletion policies, and periodic access reviews.
D3	Cybersecurity expertise	Consider in-house cybersecurity staff, professionals available through a parent organization, and contracted or managed security service providers. Assess whether the expertise is actively engaged in repository operations, not just nominally available.

Section E: Crisis Response & Recovery

Please rate each statement by selecting the option that best reflects your current repository practices.

1 = Not in Place 2 = Limited / ad hoc 3 = Partially in place 4 = Mostly in place 5 = Fully in place

If a question does not apply to your repository, you may select N/A, but please use this option sparingly. Additional guidance and examples for each question are provided in the table below.

Crisis Response & Recovery*

	1	2	3	4	5	N/A
E1. To what extent are repository staff equipped and able to perform critical operations remotely if physical access to facilities is lost?	()	()	()	()	()	()
E2. To what extent can the repository electronically transfer critical datasets in a timely manner during an emergency?	()	()	()	()	()	()
E3. To what extent is the repository capable of physically relocating or shipping datasets on short notice?	()	()	()	()	()	()
E4. To what extent does the repository have a documented and tested disaster recovery plan that covers a range of crisis scenarios?	()	()	()	()	()	()
E5. To what extent is the repository's software prepared for rapid redeployment in the event of a system failure or emergency?	()	()	()	()	()	()
E6. To what extent does the repository have a documented internal communication plan for coordinating staff during a crisis?	()	()	()	()	()	()
E7. To what extent is the repository able to provide timely notice of service disruptions (whether planned or unexpected) to users and the broader community?	()	()	()	()	()	()
E8. To what extent has the repository identified and documented the systems, organizations, and communities that depend on its data for critical operations?	()	()	()	()	()	()
E9. To what extent can third-party applications and automated systems continue to access the repository's data if the repository experiences a disruption?	()	()	()	()	()	()
E10. To what extent can downstream users continue to access the repository's data if the repository experiences a disruption?	()	()	()	()	()	()
E11. To what extent has the repository prioritized its datasets for recovery in the event of partial or complete data loss?	()	()	()	()	()	()

Supporting Guidance

This section evaluates the repository's ability to respond to and recover from an active crisis, including maintaining data access for users and dependent systems during a disruption.

Use the descriptions below for additional guidance when answering the questions in this section.

#	Question	Guidance
E1	Remote work capability	Consider whether remote access to systems is available, secure, and tested, and whether staff have the equipment and connectivity needed to work effectively offsite.
E2	Electronic data transfer capability	Consider whether available bandwidth is sufficient relative to total data volume for time-sensitive transfers.
E3	Physical data transfer capability	Consider whether procedures and materials such as hard drives and packaging are prepared in advance and whether staff are trained to execute a physical transfer quickly.
E4	Disaster recovery planning	Consider whether the plan addresses natural disasters, cyberattacks, funding loss, and personnel loss, and whether it is reviewed and tested on a regular schedule.
E5	Software redeployment readiness	Consider whether installation images, backups, and configuration snapshots are maintained and regularly tested to ensure the software can be restored quickly with minimal downtime.
E6	Internal crisis communication	Consider whether staff have clear escalation paths, emergency contact information, and defined roles and responsibilities during a crisis scenario.
E7	Public disruption notices	Consider whether communication channels such as website notices, mailing lists, social media, and professional society communications are in place and can be activated quickly in the event of both planned maintenance and unexpected outages.
E8	Downstream dependencies	Consider whether a dependency map or registry exists, and whether dependent parties have been notified of continuity arrangements.
E9	Third-party application continuity	Consider whether alternate API endpoints, federated mirrors, or redundant data feeds are in place to prevent automated pipelines from failing during an outage.
E10	User access continuity	Consider whether alternate access points, mirrors, or cached copies are available to users during an outage, and whether users are informed of where to find data if primary access is unavailable.
E11	Dataset recovery prioritization	Consider whether datasets are tiered by criticality, and whether recovery sequences are documented and integrated into the disaster recovery plan.

Section F: Networks, Partnerships & Community

Please rate each statement by selecting the option that best reflects your current repository practices.

1 = Not in Place 2 = Limited / ad hoc 3 = Partially in place 4 = Mostly in place 5 = Fully in place

If a question does not apply to your repository, you may select N/A, but please use this option sparingly. Additional guidance and examples for each question are provided in the table below.

Networks, Partnerships & Community*

	1	2	3	4	5	N/A
F1. To what extent does the repository have formal agreements with external or internal partners for data replication or archival support in a crisis?	()	()	()	()	()	()
F2. To what extent does the repository have formal agreements with external or internal partners for operational support in a crisis?	()	()	()	()	()	()
F3. To what extent does the repository actively engage its user community, key stakeholders, and external partners in resilience and continuity planning?	()	()	()	()	()	()

Supporting Guidance

This section evaluates the repository's external and internal relationships that could provide critical support in a crisis.

Use the descriptions below for additional guidance when answering the questions in this section.

#	Question	Guidance
F1	Data replication and archival agreements	Consider whether agreements such as MOUs or data sharing arrangements are in place with peer repositories, professional networks, or units within the parent organization, and whether these agreements are documented and actionable.
F2	Operational support agreements	Consider whether agreements are in place with peer organizations, IT departments, or other units within the parent organization to support continued operations, and whether these agreements are documented and actionable.
F3	Community and stakeholder engagement	Consider whether users and stakeholders have been informed of continuity arrangements, whether citizen archivists or external partners are supported in backing up holdings, and whether channels exist for the community to provide input on resilience priorities.

Section G: Sustainability & Continuity

Please rate each statement by selecting the option that best reflects your current repository practices.

1 = Not in Place 2 = Limited / ad hoc 3 = Partially in place 4 = Mostly in place 5 = Fully in place

If a question does not apply to your repository, you may select N/A, but please use this option sparingly. Additional guidance and examples for each question are provided in the table below.

Sustainability & Continuity*

	1	2	3	4	5	N/A
G1. To what extent does the repository have documented plans for migrating datasets or systems to updated formats, tools, or platforms?	()	()	()	()	()	()
G2. To what extent does the repository have a documented shutdown plan that ensures data is preserved and responsibly transferred if operations cease?	()	()	()	()	()	()
G3. To what extent does the repository have a formal, executable agreement with another national repository to assume its holdings if it can no longer operate?	()	()	()	()	()	()
G4. To what extent does the repository have a formal, executable agreement with an international repository to assume its holdings if it can no longer operate?	()	()	()	()	()	()
G5. To what extent does the repository have a clear continuity plan if its parent institution undergoes a significant organizational crisis?	()	()	()	()	()	()
G6. To what extent are the repository's funding sources diversified such that losing a single source would not threaten continued operations?	()	()	()	()	()	()

Supporting Guidance

This section evaluates the repository's long-term viability, including funding stability, system migration planning, and formal agreements to preserve holdings if the repository can no longer operate.

Use the descriptions below for additional guidance when answering the questions in this section.

#	Question	Guidance
G1	Data and systems migration planning	Consider whether migration tools are available, plans are tested, and community input is incorporated.
G2	Shutdown and data transfer planning	Consider whether the plan covers data handoff, system decommissioning, and staff transition.
G3	National continuity agreement	Consider whether the agreement is signed, detailed, and has been reviewed for feasibility.
G4	International continuity agreement	Consider whether the agreement is signed, detailed, and has been reviewed for feasibility. Mark N/A if international continuity is outside the scope of this repository's mandate.
G5	Parent institution continuity planning	Examples of institutional crises include severe budget cuts, institutional restructuring, or closure.
G6	Funding diversity	Reliance on a single funding stream scores lowest. Multiple roughly equivalent funding streams that collectively sustain operations scores highest.

Report Page

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Confirm Report Download

On the previous page, you had the option to download or save a copy of your RCS report.

If you have not saved your report, please use the **Back** button to return to the report page and download or save a copy.

5) Have you saved a copy of your RCS report?*

- Yes, I have downloaded or saved my RCS report.
 - No, I need to go back and save my RCS report before submitting.
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Save Your Responses

Scroll Down to the bottom of the page and select "Download PDF Version" to save a copy of your form responses.

This copy includes the answers you submitted throughout the RCS, which may be useful for internal review, team discussion, or future comparison if you retake the RCS.

Please save a copy before continuing if you would like to keep a record of your responses.

Confirm Responses Saved

On the previous page, you had the option to download or save a copy of your **RCS Responses**.

If you have not saved your **responses**, please use the **Back** button to return to the previous page and download or save a copy.

6) Have you saved a copy of your Responses to the RCS?*

- Yes, I have downloaded or saved my Responses to the RCS.
 - No, I need to go back and save my Responses before submitting.
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Thank You!

Thank you for completing the Repository Crisis Scorecards. We hope your results support reflection, confirm existing strengths, and help identify opportunities to further strengthen your repository.
